

Emigration, Its Socio-Economic and Demographic Impacts on The People of St. Estevam Census Town in Goa

Soniya Parab¹, Ms. Sunayana Haldankar² & Prof. (Dr.) P. K. Rath³

¹MA II Geography student, Government College, Khandola – Marcela, Goa.

²Assistant Professor of Geography and Research Scholar – CRC in Geography, Government College, Khandola – Marcela, Goa.

³Professor of Geography, PG Department and CRC in Geography, Government College, Khandola – Marcela, Goa.

Corresponding Author – Soniya Parab

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18477442

Abstract:

Emigration has been an important part of Goa's social and economic life from the colonial era. This study portrays the emigration scenario from St. Estevam (Census Town Jua) in Tiswadi taluka of North Goa. Many families in the village have members working abroad or on cruise ships and migration has continued over a long period. The main aim of the study is to understand why people migrate, identify migration trends and examine how emigration affects families and the village they leave behind. The study uses both primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected from 120 emigrant households through structured questionnaires, interviews and field observations. These households were selected using purposive and snowball sampling methods. Secondary data were taken from the Census of India 2011 and Panchayat records. The analysis uses simple methods like percentage and frequency analysis.

The findings show that people migrate mainly because of limited job opportunities in the native place and the desire for better income and living conditions. Money sent home by migrants has helped improve housing, living standards, asset ownership and financial stability considerably. At the same time, emigration has created several challenges, viz. ageing population, shortage of local labour, weakening of cultural practices and emotional stress for family members who stay behind.

The study concludes that emigration is an important source of income and development for St. Estevam. However, it has changed the village's social and demographic structure highlighting the need for better local development policies that addresses the concerns at the place of origin.

Keywords: Emigration, Impacts, Demographic change, Remittances, Rural Livelihoods.

Introduction:

Emigration is the act of leaving one's country or region to settle in another. It describes the departure of people from their home country with the intention of establishing a new residence elsewhere. (International Organization for Migration, 2019). People emigrate for various reasons, including seeking better economic opportunities, escaping political or religious persecution, or moving for family reunification. When people leave a country, they lower the

nation's labor force and consumer spending. (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2020). When people emigrate to a new country, they pay taxes in the new country based on earnings, property owned, and other factors. They may also pay sales tax on purchases when applicable. Many countries regulate the number of people that can emigrate or immigrate from one country to another. (U.S. Department of Homeland Security, 2023).

At the national level, especially in developing countries like India, emigration often acts as a survival strategy for households. Limited employment opportunities, low wages and economic insecurity encourage people to seek work outside their region or country. Migration helps households manage financial risks and meet every day needs through remittances sent back home.

Goa has a long history of emigration dating back to the colonial period. Due to limited local employment and strong migration networks, many Goans have moved abroad, particularly to Europe, the Middle East and the maritime sector. Emigration has significantly influenced household incomes and living standards through remittances. At the same time, it has led to social and demographic changes such as an ageing population, increased responsibilities for women, and changes in family structures.

St. Estevam in Tiswadi taluka of North Goa is a typical migrant-sending village where emigration is a common livelihood practice. Many households have at least one member working abroad or on cruise ships. While emigration has improved economic conditions for many families, its social and demographic impacts are complex. Since village-level studies on these issues are limited, this study focuses on understanding the patterns, causes and effects of emigration in St. Estevam, with special reference to household-level socio-economic and demographic changes.

Objectives:

The study to understand the understand why people migrate, identify migration trends and examine how emigration affects families and the village they leave behind.

Data Source and Methodology:

The study uses both primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected from emigrant households in St. Estevam village through household surveys, interviews and field visits. A semi-structured questionnaire was used with households that had at least one member working abroad. It collected information on reasons for migration, destination countries, remittances and their effects on household living conditions. In addition, semi-structured interviews were carried out to understand the experiences and views of family members who stayed behind. A total of 120 emigrant households were selected. Households were first chosen using purposive sampling and then snowball sampling was used to identify more migrant-sending families. Secondary data were collected from the Census of India 2011, Panchayat records, government reports and academic publications. Data analysis included simple quantitative methods such as percentages and frequency analysis, age–sex composition and patterns of remittance use. These were presented using charts and age pyramids. Qualitative analysis was used to study the reasons for emigration and its social and cultural effects, including changes in household roles, population ageing and community life.

Study Area:

According to the 2011 Census, St. Estevam (in Tiswadi Taluka, North Goa) St. Estevam is a small village in the Tiswadi taluka of North Goa, is geographically situated at approximately 15°32'23"N latitude and 73°57'73"E longitude with a rural, coastal setting. The village has a population of around 5000 and a literacy rate estimated to be between 90%. St. Estevam is an Island in Tiswadi, Goa. It is encircled by the Mandovi River on all sides and was connected to the mainland by the bridge only

in the mid 1980's. Also known as Juvem and in the past it was known as Shakecho Juvo - the isle of vegetables. Santo Estevao is most famous for its premium seven-ridged, light-green and long lady finger or okra. That's why many people refer to villagers as 'bhendde'. Juvem is the fourth largest island in Goa. This Island originally consisted of three small islets Jua, Tolto and Vantso with a canal connecting them. These small islets have been joined together into one island that is Santo Estevam. Juvem is rich in historical heritage and natural beauty. There is a fort situated here on a hillock which was built in September 1668. It was named as the fort of St Francis Xavier and is also known as the fort of Jua.

Fig. 1: Study Area Map

Source: Prepared by Researcher using SoI Toposheet in QGIS module.

Results And Discussion:

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondent Households:

The socio-demographic details of the surveyed households (Table 1) help in understanding the structure of emigrant families in St. Estevam village. Most respondents belong to the 41 - 60 years age group (43.33%), followed by those aged 25 - 40 years (33.33%). Only a small share of respondents are below 25 years (10.83%) or above 60 years (12.33%). This shows that middle-aged adults mainly handle household responsibilities and migration-related decisions, while many elderly family members remain in the village. Women form the majority of respondents, making up (74.16%) while men account for 25.83%. This is mainly because many working-age men have migrated abroad for jobs. As a result, women manage households and family matters, showing a clear increase in their role in decision-making.

In terms of education, most respondents are fairly educated. About (43.33%) have completed higher secondary education and 36.66% are graduates. Only a small proportion have primary-level education. This level of education may help families understand migration opportunities and manage remittance income better. Regarding family type, (76.66%) of households are nuclear families, while (23.33%) are joint families. This reflects changing family patterns influenced by migration and physical separation of family members. The shift towards nuclear families has implications for elderly care and social support within the village.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Profile of Respondent Households of St. Estevam, 2025

Variable	Category	Count (n = 120)	Percentage
Age group	Below 25	13	10.83
	25–40	40	33.33
	41–60	52	43.33
	Bove 60	15	12.33
Gender	Male	31	25.83
	Female	89	74.16
Education	Primary	10	8.33
	Secondary	9	7.5
	Higher Secondary	52	43.33
	Graduate	44	36.66
	Post Graduation	5	4.16
Type of Family	Nuclear	92	76.66
	Joint	28	23.33

Source: Compiled by Authors using Field data.

Reasons for Emigration from St. Estevam:

Economic reasons are the main cause of emigration from St. Estevam (Fig. 2). Nearly (49.16%) of respondents reported a lack of local employment as the main reason for migration. This shows the limited job opportunities available within the village. Another (35.83%) migrated in search of a better lifestyle, including higher

income and improved living conditions. Smaller proportions cited influence of relatives (5.83%) and low local wages (5%). Very few migrated for education (3.33%) or purely for higher income abroad (0.83%). Overall, emigration is mainly driven by economic insecurity and the desire for a better quality of life.

Table 2: Reasons for Emigration from St. Estevam, 2025

Reasons for Emigration	Count (n = 120)	Percentage
Lack of local employment	59	49.16
Low wages locally	6	5.0
Better income abroad	1	0.83
Family/relative influence	7	5.83
Better lifestyle	43	35.83
Education opportunities	4	3.33

Source: Compiled by Authors using Field data.

Fig. 2: Reasons for Emigration from St. Estevam, 2025

Source: Compiled by Authors using Field data.

Distribution of Emigrants by Country of Destination:

Most emigrants from the village move to a few selected destinations (Fig. 3). The United Kingdom, especially London, is the most preferred destination, accounting for (42.53%) of emigrants. This reflects strong migration networks and long-standing connections. Dubai is the second most common destination (24.62%), followed by other Gulf countries (11.94%). Countries like Australia (8.95%) and Thailand (7.46%) attract a moderate number of migrants. Very few migrate to countries such as Japan, Germany, or Mexico due to higher costs, language issues, and stricter immigration rules. These patterns show that migration is strongly influenced by existing networks.

Fig. 3: Emigrants Distribution According to Country of Destination from St. Estevam, 2025

Source: Compiled by Authors using Field data.

Table 3: Occupational Characteristics of Emigrants from St. estevam in Destinations, 2025

Occupation Abroad	Count (n=120)	Percentage
Service sector	19	16.0
Cruise liner	74	61.0
Skilled jobs	20	17.0
Others	7	6.0

Source: Compiled by Authors using Field data.

Occupational Characteristics of Emigrants Abroad:

Most emigrants are employed in service-based jobs. A large share (61.66%) work as cruise liners, showing Goa's strong link with maritime employment. Skilled jobs account for (16.66%) while (15.83%) work in general service sectors. Only a small number are involved in other occupations. This indicates a heavy dependence on overseas contract-based work, with limited access to highly skilled jobs. The predominance of cruise liner employment indicates strong demand for labour in the maritime and hospitality sectors, supported by higher earnings, contractual job security, and established recruitment networks. The relatively lower share of skilled and service-sector employment suggests limited access to high-skilled overseas jobs due to factors such as qualification requirements and skill barriers. Overall, the findings highlight a concentration of emigrants in service-oriented occupations abroad, with important implications for income generation and remittance flows.

Fig. 4: Occupational Characteristics of Emigrants from St. Estevam in Destinations

Duration of Stay of Emigrants Abroad:

The analysis of duration of stay (Table 4) reveals that emigration from St. Estevam is

largely temporary to medium-term in nature. The majority of emigrants (58.33%) have stayed abroad for 2 - 5 years, followed by (18.33%) who have remained abroad for 6–10 years. Short-term migration of less than two years accounts for (16.66%) of respondents, while only (6.66%) have stayed abroad for more than ten years. This pattern indicates that most migrants maintain strong ties with their place of origin and view migration as a temporary strategy to improve household income rather than permanent settlement. The prevalence of medium-term migration highlights the importance of remittances and return migration in sustaining village-level livelihoods.

Table 4: Distribution Pattern of Emigrants According to Stay Duration in Destinations

Duration staying in abroad	Count (n=120)	Percentage
less than 2 years	20	16.66
2-5 years	70	58.33
6-10 years	22	18.33
More than 10 years	8	6.66

Source: Compiled by Authors using Field data.

Fig. 5: Distribution Pattern of Emigrants According to Stay Duration in Destinations, 2025

Source: Compiled by Authors using Field data.

on relatively small but regular remittance flows. About (48.33%) of households receive less than ₹10,000 per month, while 44.16% receive between ₹10,000 and ₹25,000. Only a small proportion of households receive higher remittance amounts, with 4.16% receiving ₹ 25,001–Rs. 50,000 and (3.33%) receiving more than ₹ 50,000. This uneven distribution highlights income disparities among emigrant households and suggests that while remittances are crucial for daily household expenses, their potential for substantial savings or investment is limited for most families.

Remittances Received by the Emigrant Households:

The distribution of remittances received by households shows that most families depend

Table 5: Remittances Received by the Emigrant Households of St. Estevam, 2025:

Amount	Count (n=120)	Percentage
<10,000	58	48.33
10,000–25,000	53	44.16
25,001–50,000	5	4.16
>50,000	4	3.33

Source: Compiled by Authors using Field data.

Utilization of Remittances by Households:

The pattern of remittance utilization shows that remittances are mainly used for household consumption. A large majority of households (70.83%) spend remittance income on daily needs such as food, utilities, and routine expenses. Savings and investment account for 14.16%, indicating limited capacity for long-term

financial planning. House construction accounts for 7.5% of remittance use, reflecting investment in housing improvement. Very small proportions are spent on education, healthcare, and business activities (2.5% each). This pattern suggests that remittances primarily support immediate household needs rather than productive or income-generating activities

Table 6: Remittances and Their Utilization by Emigrant Households at St. Estevam, 2025

Use of Remittance	Count (n=120)	Percentage
Household needs	85	70.83
Education	3	2.5
Healthcare	3	2.5
House construction	9	7.5
Savings/investment	17	14.16
Business	3	2.5

Source: Compiled by Authors using Field data.

Fig. 6: Remittances and their Utilization by Emigrant Households at St. Estevam, 2025

Source: Compiled by Authors using Field data.

Social and Cultural Impact of Emigration:

socio-cultural impacts of emigration are evident in changes at both household and community levels. A majority of respondents reported an increase in women's decision-making roles, reflecting the growing responsibility of women in managing households in the absence of migrant members. However, cultural practices and participation in festivals show a decline, indicating reduced social interaction and weakening of traditional community life. The findings suggest that while emigration has empowered women and improved household income security, it has also contributed to social challenges such as reduced cultural participation,

emotional stress, and increased caregiving responsibilities for the elderly.

Conclusion:

The present study highlights that emigration from St. Estevam village is primarily driven by economic factors such as lack of local employment opportunities, low wages, and aspirations for a better lifestyle. The findings reveal a strong concentration of migrants in specific destinations, particularly the United Kingdom and Middle Eastern countries, supported by established migrant networks. Emigration has significantly influenced household structures, resulting in a predominance of nuclear families and increased responsibilities for women left behind. Remittances play a crucial role in sustaining household livelihoods, mainly fulfilling daily consumption needs, though their use for productive investments remains limited. Overall, while emigration has contributed positively to household income security, it has also led to socio-cultural changes, including reduced participation in traditional practices and increased caregiving burdens on the remaining population, especially women and the elderly.

Recommendations and Suggestions:

Based on the findings, it is recommended that local and state authorities focus on generating sustainable employment opportunities within the village through skill-development programmes, promotion of small-scale industries, and support for entrepreneurship. Policies should encourage productive utilisation of remittances by providing financial literacy training and incentives for investment in education, healthcare, and local businesses. Special attention should be given to women-headed households through social security schemes and community support systems, as women play an increasingly central role in household management. Strengthening rural infrastructure and improving access to

quality education and healthcare may reduce distress-driven migration and enhance overall socio-economic development in the study area.

Limitations of the Study:

The analysis is based on a relatively small sample size of 120 households, which may limit the generalisation of findings to other villages or regions. The use of purposive and snowball sampling techniques may introduce respondent bias, as households with stronger migration networks were more likely to be included.

References:

1. IOM (International Organization for Migration). (2019). World migration report 2020. IOM.
2. OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development). (2013). International migration outlook 2013. OECD Publishing.
3. OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development). (2022). International migration outlook 2022. OECD Publishing.
4. United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs. (2020). International migration 2020 highlights. United Nations.
5. U. S. Department of Homeland Security. (2023). Yearbook of immigration statistics 2022. Office of Immigration Statistics.
6. Ostra, V. A., & Yavorska, V. V. (2025). DEMOGRAPHIC CRISIS AND MIGRATION PROCESSES: INTERRELATION AND IMPLICATIONS FOR SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT. *Odesa National University Herald. Geography and Geology*, 30(1(46)).
7. Lupak, R., Mizyuk, B., Zaychenko, V., Kynytska-Iliash, M., & Vasylytsiv, T. (2022). MIGRATION PROCESSES AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: INTERACTIONS AND REGULATORY POLICY. *Agricultural and Resource Economics*.